

Tectonic Fracture Analysis, Remote sensing, GIS, and Geophysical Characterization for Groundwater Exploration in the Red Sea Hills, Sudan

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The northwestern part of the Red Sea Hills, within the Hamisana region of Sudan is characterized by an arid desert climate and suffers from severe water scarcity. Most people living in these regions suffer from lack of water due to the complicated geological structure, which requires high-method analysis to locate invisible aquifers, enhance water extraction, and secure long-term groundwater sustainability.

This study aims to integrate structural analysis with remote sensing techniques to identify the most promising fracture zones for groundwater occurrence in hard rock terrains. Fracture extension and shear fractures in basement terrains are the power key pathways for groundwater movement, directly controlling storage and recharge in arid regions.

Ductile deformation features in the study area were delineated using Landsat imagery and measurements through field observations. Structural analysis was conducted to classify fractures within the hard rock formations according to the force or direction of collision. Stress-strain analysis was applied to differentiate potential open fractures (extensional, tensional, and release fractures) from closed shear fractures. The results of stress and strain analysis indicate that extensional fractures trend northwest-southeast, while release fractures trend northeast-southwest. Over time, due to runoff, weathering, and erosion, some of these fractures evolve into wadis, which can serve as significant groundwater storage zones, corresponding to the first collision between the Haya and Gabiét terrains. Additionally, east-west extensional fractures and north-south release fractures were identified linked to the second collision between the Gabgba and Gabiét terrains.

To further investigate groundwater potential, electrical resistivity geophysical methods were employed to determine the depth (ranging from 40 to 60 m), thickness, and lithological variations of both alluvial and basement aquifers. Geographic Information Systems (GIS) and specialized computer programs were utilized to process and visualize the data, enhancing the interpretation of structural and geophysical findings.

These techniques are significant and used extensively to detect the aquifer in basement terrain and to understand groundwater movement and accumulation through classification fracture and direction of lineament analysis.

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